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Postmodern University Understanding: Organizational and Managerial Aspects

Abstract: *Introduction.* In the modern world, the university acquires new characteristics and functions, where traditional values are complemented by new ones which are connected with development of the regional community and entry to the international level. That is why the postmodern university should reorient its managerial and organizational levers. *Purpose and methods.* The purpose of the article is to consider the university as a driver of regional development through the analysis of its modern management. The study of postmodern university requires the use of multidisciplinary socio-cultural, structural and functional approaches and historical, analytical, comparative methods. *Results.* Universities that have always strived not only for knowledge for the sake of knowledge, but also for reproduction of knowledge for the sake of growth and strengthening of society well-being, must change the managerial paradigm. And such postmodern education institutions can be drivers of socio-economic development and scientific-educational potential. *Conclusions and discussion.* Modern universities have to become the growth points of the regions and take an active part in solving educational, socio-economic and cultural issues. Management of higher school should be aimed at ensuring its competitiveness both

in the internal and external markets of educational services. The scientific novelty of the obtained results is to determine the factors of development of the postmodern university as a driver of growth of economy and socio-cultural sphere of the region. The practical significance of the obtained results is reflected in the possibility of using the idea of the university as a point of growth of the region and the country.

Keywords: university, postmodern university, university management, socio-cultural space management, university as a driver, university as a point of growth.

1. Introduction

The problem formulation. The socio-cultural, economic and political changes taking place in Ukraine influence directly higher education. Nowadays, the university, as the brightest representative of higher education, has been given the opportunity to determine its own mechanisms of adaptation to the new postmodern reality. In conditions of power transformation, changes in the value system, identity and structuring of society in the context of globalization, postmodern universities acquire new characteristics and functions, where traditional values are complemented by completely new ones, which are connected with development of the regional community and entry to the international level. That is why the postmodern university should reorient its managerial and organizational levers, while at the same time independently form the scientific and cultural potential of the regional and national elite. Thus, the role of management in the activities of the postmodern university is constantly growing and acquiring new qualities.

Any modern university lives and functions in a certain socio-cultural space, where its formation is influenced by both historical development of the region, country, and various cultural, social, labor, economic, ethical orientations and traditions. Also an important role in development of the socio-cultural space of the university is played by geographical location, the level of socio-economic development of the region, the degree of migration activity of the population, the possibility of active interaction with other regions and countries.

The relevance of this study is due not only to changes and new requirements for modern education. Nowadays, educational management gains great importance as a management system aimed at ensuring competitiveness both at the internal and external markets of the educational services at the expense of high quality education and training of high-level specialists with principled civic position and moral qualities. This is necessary for development and further modernization of the higher education system itself and also for increasing the role of universities in the socio-cultural and economic life of the regions, as well as for the successful representation of the university in the

world in general. Postmodern thinking, which opens up the space for open dialogue, also puts certain requirements on higher education institutions, which must be primarily in demand in the region, which means that they are entrusted with very important tasks, namely: training personnel required by the region, taking into account the needs of industry and employers; conducting scientific research relevant to socio-economic development; active participation of the university in the socio-cultural life of both the region and the country, as well as its recognition in the world. At the same time, the postmodern university is in an environment of extreme instability and turbulence, which is explained by a number of different factors of influence to which the existing system of education is exposed. Trends of modern society development – globalization, post-industrialization, transnationalization, serviceization, aesthetization, financization, gamization, informatization – affect the higher education system, thereby changing the relationships between the university, governing bodies and business.

These trends shift the emphasis of public policy in the innovations management towards processes of interaction between them and make relevant the studies of the specifics of their interaction. In such a situation, universities can accumulate knowledge, technologies and innovations that are aimed at developing entrepreneurial skills (Chatterton & Goddard, 2000). In recent decades, there have also been significant changes in the character of universities' relationships with consumers of their products and services. Therefore, the leading role of the University is to change its mission and functions.

State study of the problem. An analysis of recent research and publications that began to investigate the problems of the modern higher education institution and its understanding as a socio-cultural space is impossible without considering and clarifying the essence of certain definitions, such as “space”, “social space”, “socio-cultural space” and “management of education”.

In modern Western philosophy, the problem of space, social space, for example, was considered by G. Simmel (2018), who tried to consider society through the inner life of man, using such concepts as “spirit of the time”, “everyday human existence”.

Understanding of the social space and its various forms (economic, legal, cultural, etc.) has been considered in the works of many researchers, such as M. Weber (1994), E. Durkheim (2008), J. Moreno (2004), T. Parsons (2000) and others.

A rather interesting theory of social space was developed by P. Bourdieu (2001), who understands it as an organized form of economic, social and cultural capital.

In Ukrainian science, various researchers have also addressed the problems of social space. Understanding of the environment as a set of conditions of man and society existence is considered in the works of L. Males (2007), the state and dynamics of social change, social reality is revealed in the works of O. Stehni (2010).

To the concept of “socio-cultural space” first paid attention the Russian-American philosopher P. Sorokin (2008), who represented it as a set of three elements – meanings, values and norms; conductors; human agents (p. 162). Many researchers considered the concept of socio-cultural space as the unity of culture and society, which is the basic understanding of this definition in view of the specified problem. Thus, E. Durkheim (2008) emphasized the decisive sociocultural significance of the phenomena of social life in the spiritual development of the individual.

Various aspects of the problem of educational management have been considered in the works of E. Kovalenko (2015), Ya. Martynshyn and O. Khlystun (2018), B. Readings (2010), E. Saburova (2009) and other scientists.

In view of this, leading scientists note that the principles of postmodern culture, i.e., destruction of the antagonism between scientific and non-scientific cognitive practices, deepening of the integration of scientific and educational spaces, become acute (Habermas, 2000; Koslowski, 1997; Lyotard, 1998) and others).

Unresolved issues. The analysis of the scientific literature shows that Western and native science have accumulated sufficient experience in consideration of a higher education institution both as an educational establishment and social environment. But the University as a point of growth of the region and the country has not been sufficiently explored. This circumstance determines the choice of the topic of research and the purpose – to conduct a socio-philosophical analysis of organizational and managerial aspects of the university, which create conditions for the university functioning as a point of growth of socio-cultural and economic environment of the region and the country.

2. Purpose and research methods

The purpose of the article. University, as the institution of higher education, which traditionally performs the function of providing educational services and conducting research, began to study at the end of the XVIII century. But the modern university and its postmodern understanding, needs new research, new methods and approaches.

Therefore, the purpose of the article is to analyze organizational and managerial aspects of the university as a specific spatio-temporal entity of the

postmodern higher education institution, where all subjects interact (educational component, social component, economic component, institutions of culture and arts, public organizations, business sphere, etc.), which should be drivers for the development of the region.

The methodological basis of the study. The methodological basis of the research is grounded on the concepts of philosophy, culturology, sociology, economics, which consider a higher education institution (university) as an important element of social life and personality formation. A systematic and comprehensive philosophical understanding of the managerial and organizational aspects of postmodern university activity determines the theoretical value of this research. Consideration and analysis of such an education institution as university is based on the principles of objectivity, systematicity and determinism.

The most productive is consideration of the socio-cultural space in terms of the systems approach, bearing in mind that within its boundaries socio-cultural activity is realized: creation of cultural values; development of individuals' abilities and maintenance of their creative activity; communication – dissemination, preservation and public use of all kinds of cultural values, i.e. satisfaction and formation of individual-cultural and socio-cultural needs. With the help of the systems approach, the university is considered as the entity with harmonious functioning of all elements and parts.

The socio-cultural approach is used to analyze components of the socio-cultural space: individual as a subject of interaction, society as a set of interacting individuals with sociocultural relations and processes, culture as a set of meanings, values and norms possessed by interacting individuals.

The structural-functional approach helps to investigate the integrity of the object (university) in which each element has a specific functional purpose. This approach allows exploring various connections of the components of the whole.

Research methods. In order to achieve the set goal in the work the methods of anthropological and social interpretation have been used, which allow to trace connections between changes in the social environment and consciousness transformation. Methods of analysis, synthesis, systematization and generalization make it possible to order the studies of domestic and foreign researchers on development and changes in the functions of universities. Systems-structural, structural-functional methods have been applied in order to outline the managerial and organizational activity of universities as drivers of regional growth.

Research information base. The information base of the study is diverse sources concerning consideration of universities from the moment of their origination to the present day; theoretical and methodological developments

of Western, domestic and Russian researchers dedicated to the study of higher education institutions (universities) directly, as well as their transformation at the present stage. In addition, we used personal observations on the activities of leading higher education institutions in Ukraine and, directly, on the managerial and organizational aspects of Sumy State University.

3. Research results

The role of the university in the formation of cultural space has been studied in detail by various scholars in our country and abroad, in the framework of considering various aspects of this process: social, economic, gender, political, etc. The tradition of the study of the formation and essence of the university as a special socio-cultural phenomenon emerged in the early XIII century and the subject of study was the activity of English universities, first of all, Oxford, Cambridge and Dublin.

One of the oldest histories of the University of Cambridge was published in 1721, based on the Latin works of two different authors: *N. Cantalupus*, a Prior of the Carmelites Order, who lived in England in the first half of the 15th century, and the Rev. *R. Parker*, who taught at one of colleges of Cambridge (Parker & Cantalupus, 1721). Later, the works of these two authors were expanded by the work of other researchers with the list of rectors of the university and the list of privileges granted to the university by English monarchs. It is noteworthy that during this period in England appeared works, which contained a critique of university traditions.

In the second half of the XVIII century appeared a galaxy of historians who devoted their books to the study of English universities, most notably Oxford and Cambridge. As a rule, they were all university professors, for example, *E. Carter* (1753). Also in the XIX century were published the works devoted not only to leading English, but also to American universities.

However, the above mentioned scientists described only specific universities, and only in the XX century started recognition of the university as a very important historical and cultural phenomenon that defined the cultural environment in its region, and sometimes throughout the country. Among such works we will call the monograph of the Spanish philosopher *J. Ortega y Gasset* (2010) "University Mission", where he analyzes in detail the role played by the university in modern society and which has become widespread in university circles.

The relationships between university and society were also analyzed by the Italian historian and philosopher *A. Gramsci* (1991), who largely predicted those structural and philosophical changes that affected Western university at the end of the XX century. These issues are still discussed and important for our country, namely the issues of competencies and specializations.

The works offering philosophical understanding of the problem of the university phenomenon include the monograph by Canadian philosopher *B. Readings* (2010), “The University in Ruins”, in which he attempted to understand critically the role that the university plays in modern times. The author concludes that traditional role of the university as a center of culture and science in modern society has outlived itself, and it has been replaced by another role of the transnational corporation in society.

In the second half of the XX century the scientific community paid considerable attention to the history and philosophy of the university. Since 1981, a multi-volume edition of “History of Universities” has been published, co-edited by *M. Feingold*, professor of the University of California (2011), who has endeavored to prepare the final volumes of this compendium on the history, culture and philosophy of university life.

So, based on the analysis of scientific literature, we can conclude that understanding of the essence of a higher education institution (university) has changed over the centuries from the idea of the university as a simple institution with the function of providing education to the “university in ruins”, “death of the university” and to a modern understanding of the “business university” where it is the point of growth of the region.

But postmodern present day sets new challenges and, at the same time, new opportunities to address them. Such an opportunity is understanding, and in general, functioning of the university not just as an education institution, which is “in ruins”, but as a socio-cultural space that accepts and responds to certain challenges of the present. Here we can see the ability of universities to overcome crisis phenomena, to renew the university idea, while preserving its peculiarity of socio-cultural phenomenon.

Nowadays, universities have become the mainstay of the reproduction of three important components that are necessary for further development and prosperity of a nation – highly qualified personnel, expertise and scientific developments that promote emergence of new products, technologies and so on.

As it has been noted above, in addition to the educational and research objectives, universities are now realizing themselves in the socio-cultural space of a particular region, country and even the world. This is due to the fact that universities begin to change their paradigm: they move from the traditional scientific and educational model to “University 3.0” or “third mission” in terms of Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) – international economic organization of developed countries that recognize the principles of representative democracy and a free market economy).

What is a “third mission” for a modern university? This is the impact that higher education institutions make on the economy, the level of human capital and innovative potential of the region. If earlier, education institutions could afford to remain on the periphery of the processes that take place in society, in the modern knowledge economy, they find themselves at the epicenter of events. That is why the third function of the university is to serve the regional community, precisely because of the innovative problems that have increasingly shifted towards education institutions. For example, in Finland, higher education institutions have been assigned responsibility for innovative development of the regions, taking into account the existing structure of the economy. To fulfill these tasks, they ensure the continuity of education, interact with business, industry and other sectors of the labor market, as well as with other universities, both Finnish and foreign.

So, we can say that the “third role” is interaction of universities with business. Foreign universities started instilling in their students not only knowledge but also an entrepreneurial spirit. The significant effect of such changes can be seen on the example of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. And there is enough examples where universities act as entrepreneurial structures. Certainly, to achieve such results, large-scale work of managers, generation of innovations inside the university, formation of innovative systems, advancement of developments outside are required.

There are a lot of tools by which universities can influence the regional community. Modern universities are economic actors, being both employers and taxpayers. They are the main source of innovations and scientific-technological advancements. Universities and the education system need to train people to develop the region. University-based research centers are capable of creating small town and village development programs and the like. In this context *E. Saburova* (2009) states that “Universities can bring popularity to a city, region, can easily contribute to the development of a place image, but only if a joint marketing development program is created, if the city and the university exist as one whole and support each other’s capabilities” (p. 144).

Considering the university as an institution conducive to the development of a certain region, and even more – as a locomotive of economic development, special mechanisms are needed to manage the processes of creating a complex multi-level connection in the system “university – economy of the region”. The mechanism that drives development and communication in modern information society is a “driver of economic growth”. That is, the university, as a driver, relying on a modern organizational-management system, combines disparate assets (material, financial, information, educational, socio-cultural, labor, etc.) into a powerful movement that changes economic reality.

Thus, exploring such a phenomenon as a present-time university, in our opinion, it would be advisable to use such a concept as a “driver”, and the university can be considered as one of the basic elements for building regional economy development strategy. In the context of the “Triple Helix” and the innovative strategy of catching up development, regional universities should become the institutional environment for innovative ideas and a new type of relationship with government and business. This may be in case the regional development and defining prerequisites and directions for implementing a regional governance policy are closely linked to the university innovative breakthrough and socio-economic growth. Among such factors a special role is played by intellectual and human resources of the region, which stimulate development of the university in particular and the region as a whole, and therefore the well-being of the local population (Vasylychenko et al., 2015).

Another important factor in the university’s function as a driver of development is generation of active academic collaboration and networking. Campuses are the nodes of academic and personal networks (interconnections), which are very large in scale. For the business of the city, universities serve as a guide to external sources of information, sources of analysis and knowledge, and industrial information. Often universities lay foundations for the formation of various associations, as was done by Waterloo University, on the basis of which the Economic Developers Association of Canada was formed. For example, in small towns, organizational capabilities of universities are important locations for conferences and other business meetings to promote business.

Besides the fact that the university is primarily an education institution, modernity, as has been noted above, sets new requirements. The postmodern university should be the focal point for the region’s economic growth, as evidenced by the ongoing monitoring of the world-wide education institutions run by the Times Higher Education (THE) international rating agency. Thus, THE University Impact Rankings assesses universities in the world in terms of the spread of positive impact on society, economy and environment. In particular, the effectiveness of existing projects implemented by the University in the field of promotion and improvement of health care, family planning and support, physical culture and sports, ensuring comfortable working conditions, equality and non-discrimination, inclusion, development and implementation of “green” technologies, participation in local, regional and state governance, etc. is evaluated.

All these aspects are part of the modern philosophy of corporate social responsibility, which is part of the so-called “third mission” of universities and consists in the active social position of universities, harmonious co-existence, interaction and constant dialogue with society, participation in solving socio-economic problems.

Focusing on the role of universities in regional development, it is impossible to stay away from such a pressing issue as development of cultural space, which affects functioning of all other areas of activity, including competent management of human resources, development of educational system, satisfaction of students' leisure and cultural needs. Therefore, universities should be not just a training base, but a socio-cultural space, which, due to management activities, can be a platform for cultural-educational, cultural-artistic, entertainment, business projects and other events of the city and the country.

If we consider the socio-cultural space of the university through the concept of *P. Sorokin* (2008), it consists of individuals as subjects of interaction, socio-cultural relations and processes and cultures, as the totality of meanings, values and norms, possessed by the individuals and the totality of carriers, that objectify, socialize and reveal these meanings (p. 164).

Thus, the socio-cultural space of the university is multifaceted and has certain features, namely: a complex multicomponent structure that includes the values of the education system, norms, functions, forms and methods; socio-cultural space is an open system, subject to constant changes under the influence of external and internal factors; socio-cultural environment is the space of joint life of the subjects of the educational process, the individual features of which are most clearly reflected in organization of the educational space; socio-cultural environment creates the basis for the personal and professional development of participants of the educational process, formation of professional and personal competences.

Organization and management of the socio-cultural space of the university is considered as a system of pedagogical actions for aligning separate internal components of this space (of different levels and properties) in order to ensure its functioning as a holistic reality, filled with a set of expedient relationships. The socio-cultural space is represented by a set of the following components:

- social (social roles and functions, professional responsibilities, professional competencies and social activity);
- cultural (values and norms of behavior, value orientations; cultural sites, etc.);
- scientific (scientific base, research activity);
- technological (forms, methods, technologies, means of training and professional activity);
- organizational (mission, principles, goals, functions, management structure, management);
- information (information base, distribution channels); as well as the system of their connections.

The university as a socio-cultural space serves as a source of constant reproduction and broadcasting of values, solving socio-cultural problems that are projected on the city and the region. In addition, the university space, in the modern world, is “multicultural” in its essence, because it brings together people with different cultural and national identities. The socio-cultural space of the university can be defined as a way of cultural existence of people within certain territorial boundaries. Cultural elaboration of a particular space creates a special value-symbolic and normative system, material and spiritual objects and special communication environment that shapes the face of the city and the region.

Further considering the postmodern university and its capacity to be a driver of development, one must dwell on the infrastructure function. Universities can provide creation and development of the infrastructure: sports facilities, convention centers, video conferencing equipment, libraries, high-speed Internet connection, and so on. Universities are often the catalysts for implementation of new technology-driven projects involving private sector funding. Thus, it can be concluded that universities are a point of growth that affects development of both the region and the country. This is due to the fact that the university acts as an employer, that is, creates jobs that exist or are created through the activities of the university, for example, through purchasing activities, facilitating start-ups, attracting students, and so on.

The university is a driver of innovations, influencing innovative research and implementation of its results, as well as creating an innovative ecosystem, or, for example, platforms for investor and research interaction, etc. (Yankovska, 2015).

The university is a factor in development of the region and the city and affects employment, development of local businesses, especially small ones, attracting students, visitors to events organized by the university, promoting local community development (for example, additional education for different categories of population). Nowadays, importance of the educational services market for the economies of the countries and their regions is increasing, as evidenced by the economic indicators of its functioning. It should be noted that in most European countries, in the structure of the education market, income from living wages exceeds income from payment for education. This is especially true for countries with free education, such as France, Germany, and the Czech Republic (Kutsenko, 2008).

So, we can agree with the opinion of *B. Clark* (2011), who calls the university “entrepreneurial university”. Manifestations of entrepreneurship in the postmodern university are seen in strengthening of the managerial principle, i.e., enhancement of the efficiency, flexibility and dynamism of the management structures; expansion of internal structure – departments,

managers engaged in establishing contacts with third-party organizations, industry, financial sphere, etc.); diversification of funding (increase in the share of funds from grants, local self-government bodies, charities, foundations, etc.); stimulation of the academic community (in parallel with organizational reforms, stimulating progress and innovation directly in the academic environment, involving it in solving immediate organizational and financial tasks, etc.); integrated entrepreneurship culture (spreading the entrepreneurial idea in the team, demonstrating practical achievements, spreading organizational values to give the entrepreneurial model the status of a real mechanism, etc.). Thus, universities are a modern powerful driver of development, fulfilling an important function of territorial development, generating a powerful potential for innovative stimulation and demonstrating the features of investment attractiveness. Thus, development of universities should become part of strategic territorial planning and policy-making.

4. Conclusions and discussion

Having considered the postmodern university, as well as its managerial and organizational component, we can conclude that such higher education institutions should be points of growth of the regions and actively participate in solving of educational, socio-economic, and cultural problems. With developed infrastructure and human resources, universities are able not only to be a factor in the economic growth of the region, but also to become drivers of innovative development. Management of higher school should be aimed at ensuring its competitiveness both in the internal and external markets of educational services.

The results of the study allow us to reach the following conclusions:

1. Universities act as a system-forming resource, driver of regional development.
2. Postmodern universities should be actively involved in addressing the educational, socio-economic, cultural issues of the region's development.
3. Management of the higher school, as a system of the higher education institution management, should be aimed at ensuring its competitiveness both in the internal and external markets of educational services at the expense of high quality of the educational process and training of high-level specialists.
4. Universities should serve as city-forming enterprises and shape the regional space of activity, providing traditional research and development, and, at the same time, be generators of innovation on the ground.
5. Postmodern universities are catalysts for implementation of projects related to new technologies, implementation of infrastructure functions and so on.

The scientific novelty of the obtained results lies in determining the factors of development of the postmodern university as a driver of growth of the economy and socio-cultural sphere of the region. Along with traditional functions of the university – educational and scientific, there is a sphere of economic activity, which includes development and transfer of technologies, commercialization of products of academic science, management of the intellectual property and so on. The results of the study indicate a new understanding of “educational management”, which can be interpreted as a new social phenomenon, on the success of which depends effectiveness of the university.

The practical significance of the obtained results is reflected in the possibility of using the idea of the university as a point of growth of the region. It is proved that scientific, socio-cultural, economic potentials of modern universities should be used as a platform for various activities.

Prospects for further scientific exploration in this direction. Prospects for further scientific exploration include a thorough study of the university managerial and organizational activities on ensuring continuity of all the levels of education with active involvement of the authorities, community members, employers, students and their parents.

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